

This folder contains the OTU and taxonomy tables for both bacterial and fungal communities associated with the samples analysed in this study. These data were generated from 16S rRNA and ITS amplicon sequencing, processed according to the pipeline in the main manuscript.

The files were used for use in downstream microbial beta-diversity analyses, specifically non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analysis.

OTU Tables:

- `otu.Bac.csv`: OTU abundance table for bacteria
- `otu.Fg.csv`: OTU abundance table for fungi

Each table contains read counts per OTU across samples. **Rows** represent OTUs, and **columns** represent individual samples.

Taxonomy Tables:

- `otu.tax.bac.csv`: Assigned taxonomy for bacterial OTUs
- `otu.tax.fg.csv`: Assigned taxonomy for fungal OTUs

Each taxonomy table includes **rows** as OTUs and **columns** for the assigned taxonomic ranks (e.g., phylum, class, order, family, genus).